

KEY INDICATORS

As a small country, with 7,749 hectares, Cyprus held rank 26 in the European Union in 2022. In terms of organic area share, it had 5.7% of its land under organic management, thus less than most member states. Like in many countries that became a member of the European Union in or after 2004, growth was exceptional, amounting to an increase of more than 100 times in the 2001 to 2022 period, whereas organic farmland "only" quadrupled in the European Union in the same time. Retail sales data is not available for Cyprus.

ORGANIC FARMLAND

2001

2022

Area* (Share of Total Farmland)

52 ha

7,749 ha (5.7%)

Area Growth from 2001 to 2022

14,802%

ORGANIC LAND USE & AQUACULTURE

2001

2022

Arable Land* (Share of Total)

N/D

4,506 ha (4.2%)

Permanent Crops* (Share of Total)

N/D

3,048 ha (11.1%)

Grassland* (Share of Total)

N/D

184 ha (11.9%)

Aquaculture Production (Share of Total)

N/D

N/D

ORGANIC OPERATORS

2001

2021

Producers (Share of Total)

15 (0%)

1,292 (3.8%)

Aquaculture Producers

N/D

N/D

Processors

N/D

70

Importers

N/D

28

ORGANIC RETAIL SALES

2001

2022

Retail Sales (Share of Total)

N/D

N/D

Per Capita Consumption

N/D

N/D

Retail Sales Growth from 2001 to 2022

N/D

Imports

N/D

39 †

Source: FiBL survey based on national data sources, Eurostat and TRACES/European Commission in the framework of the OrganicTargets4EU project

*In conversion and fully organic

KEY INDICATORS

DEVELOPMENT OF ORGANIC FARMLAND IN CYPRUS

Source: FiBL-AMI Survey, Eurostat Nic Lampkin

CAP ORGANIC POLICY SUPPORT

The Cyprus CAP strategic plan provides for a 250% increase in supported organic area compared with 2018. However, total expenditure is not forecast to grow by the same amount. Payments per hectare for horticultural and permanent crops are increased by up to 100%, while payments for arable and grassland are kept constant or reduced slightly. Conversion payments are set at the same level as maintenance in 2023, as in the previous period.

CONVERSION & MAINTENANCE

2018

2027

Land Area Supported (Change from 2018)*	4.5 kha	11 kha (+250%)
Share of Total Agricultural Area Supported*	3.5 %	9.0% (+250%)
Share of Certified Organic Area Supported (Change)*	76%	N/D
Expenditure per Year*	4 M€	5 M€ (+43%)
Expenditure per Hectare Supported*	805 €	459 € (-43%)

SHARE OF CAP RESOURCES

CAP EXP. 2023-2027 ORGANIC SHARE*

Organic Farming Support (P2)*	22 M€	100%
Eco-Schemes (P1)	45 M€	21.9%
Agri-Environment, Climate, Welfare (P2)	55 M€	
Total CAP Expenditure	450 M€	4.9%

*including in-conversion and fully organic land

CAP ORGANIC CONVERSION AND MAINTENANCE PAYMENTS FOR DIFFERENT LAND USES

INDICATOR	YEAR	FUND	GRASSLAND	ARABLE CROPS	HORTICULTURE	FRUIT CROPS	GRAPES	OLIVES
Conversion Support (€/ha)	2019	P2	450	380	600	900	900	750
	2023	P2	410	410	1200	1200	1200	1200
Change from 2019 to 2023			-9%	8%	100%	33%	33%	60%
Maintenance Support (€/ha)	2019	P2	450	380	600	900	900	750
	2023	P2	410	410	1200	1200	1200	1200
Change from 2019 to 2023			-9%	8%	100%	33%	33%	60%
Conversion Support Higher than Maintenance	2019		0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	2023		0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%

P1 (Pillar 1) European Agricultural Guarantee Fund (EAGF); P2 (Pillar 2) European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development (EAFRD) and national co-financing

NATIONAL ORGANIC ACTION PLAN

The current action plan is the first for Cyprus, with a strong emphasis on information activities, as well as on producer groups, local market development, public procurement and exports.

TARGETS

	PERIOD	LAND AREA TARGET	OTHER TARGETS
Previous Action Plan	None	None	None
Current Action Plan	2023-30	7.5% of UAA by 2025	None

KEY ACTIONS

PREVIOUS ACTION PLAN (NONE)

CURRENT ACTION PLAN (2023-2030)

PRODUCTION

CAP and RDP support for farming and aquaculture

MARKETS

Support small-scale, local and short supply chains; establishment of bio regions; increase use of green procurement and school milk/fruit schemes; export promotion; strengthen control system

INFORMATION

Public information and promotion, incl. EU logo, organic week, other events; strengthening advice and training; promoting knowledge exchange; including for aquaculture processing and retailing; research linked to Horizon Europe; market data analyses and annual report

AQUACULTURE

The organic share of total aquaculture production in Cyprus is negligible. Cyprus was not included in our analysis of the EMFF (2014-2020) and EMFAF (2021-2027) operational programmes and the Multi-annual National Strategic Plan for Aquaculture, but financial support for organic aquaculture production is referred to in the current action plan from 2023. As the funding is project specific and there is no ring-fenced organic budget, statistics on organic aquaculture support expenditure are not available.

OrganicTargets4EU
www.organictargets.eu

Project Coordinator
 Ambra De Simone
 IFOAM Organics Europe
www.organicseurope.bio

Authors
 Helga Willer
 (FiBL, Switzerland)

Nicolas Lampkin
 (Thünen-Institut, Germany)

Sabine Reinecke
 (FiBL, Switzerland)

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